

Stages of Organization of Non-Governmental Preschool Educational Organizations and the Use of Digital Technologies

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Abstract: This article provides the necessary information on the types of preschool organizations, the activities of preschool organizations and the conditions and procedure for their organization, the organization of preschool organizations in family, public private partnerships, the organization of private preschool organizations and their differences. In addition, this article provides information on the use of digital technologies in preschool educational organizations, the further development of any forms of MTTs, as well as on the issues of large-scale increase in the level of coverage of children brought up at this stage of education, and thus the thorough preparation of the younger generation with the foundation of the future for.

Keywords: Economy, Project, DPRK, infrastructure, non-governmental investment, Public-Private Partnership, legal entity, business entities, material and technical base, non-governmental sector, entrepreneur, director of MTT, personal Cabinet, Public partner.

Introduction. The development of general trends in higher education can become legalities with the repetition of positive results in the process of pedagogical research. We can include the following in such trends and laws:

- Organization of the educational process on the basis of established goals;
- step-by-step implementation of the participation of teachers and students in the organization of the general strategy of the educational process;
- determination of the theoretical knowledge and practical training of students of the higher educational institution in the field of professional activity, as well as the practical direction of preparing students for pedagogical activity, taking into account the results of Education.

The identification of these laws and trends is associated with the global task of pedagogy in the field of Higher Education, the justification of innovative pedagogical systems.

Tendency is the direction of progress, interest in something, inclination, aspiration.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS.

Types of non-governmental preschool educational organization and their organization

In Article 17 of the law “on preschool education and upbringing” of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the types of preschool educational organizations are given.

Public preschool organizations are organized by the following types:

- ✓ general type preschool organization;
- ✓ multidisciplinary specialized preschool organization;
- ✓ preschool organization with inclusive groups;
- ✓ co-ed preschool

Types of preschool educational organizations ¹

(See Table 1)

№	Types of preschool educational organizations	Types of activities of preschool educational organizations
1.	general type preschool	the implementation of the state educational program of preschool education and education is ensured in the groups of the general development direction
2.	multidisciplinary specialized preschool education organization	the implementation of the state educational program of preschool education and education for children with physical or mental disabilities in development is ensured
3.	preschool with inclusive groups educational organization	taking into account the needs and individual capabilities of children for separate education, equal opportunities are provided for their education and upbringing by harmonizing them with a healthy environment
4.	co-ed preschool	the implementation of the state educational program of preschool education and education is ensured, aimed at organizing the joint study and upbringing of children with physical or mental disabilities in development and children without developmental disabilities in separate groups in one organization, as well as in inclusive groups

Table 1. Types of preschool educational organizations

Types in non-governmental preschool educational organizations:

- ✓ family preschool;
- ✓ preschool organization in public private partnership;
- ✓ private preschool organization.

Establishment of a public private-partnership-based preschool organization. Over the last 20-year period, the number of preschool organizations in our country has decreased by more than 45 percent. This indicator had a significant impact on the coverage of preschool children in our country with preschool education, and in order to solve such a problem, there was a need to develop measures and study the experiences of advanced foreign countries. Thus, in our country "Family preschool organizations", preschool organizations of the "private "type and" state in order to create pre-school educational organizations based on" private partnerships", and to create favorable conditions for their organization, relevant decrees, decisions and measures were developed by ministries and organizations for the development of this sphere.

A "public private partnership" is a partnership between a public and a private partner based on the fact that the public can legally formalize a private partnership project in a certain period of time and pool its resources to carry it out.

The requirements for the establishment of a preschool educational organization based on"

¹ O'zbekiston Respublikasining "Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya to'g'risida" gi O'RQ-595-son 2019 yil 16-dekabr

public-private partnership “are given in the regulation of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 22, 2018 No. 944” on the procedure for the implementation of a public-private partnership in the form of the organization of a non-governmental preschool educational organization on land and. In the age of technology, skill and risk (risk) encompassed a person's life in every way. The education system is no exception. On the one hand, the risk (risk) in pedagogical activity is considered much lower than in the field of Economics.

Risk, risk-derived from the (Arabic) word for authority, to hope, to lean on, to believe, ultimately meaning to punish something no matter how.²

In case of construction of a state private partnership-based non-governmental preschool educational organization, the land role allocated for the construction of the applicant on his personal land, the monthly salaries of the working employees of the DXSH NMTT will be paid by the state side in the amount of 50%. The building, built if free land is allocated from the state side for the construction of the DPRK building, will act as a preschool Organization for up to 30 years, and the land allocated from the state side will become the property of the entrepreneur. In this situation, the director of the DXSH NMTT pays the monthly salaries of working employees at the expense of the children's contribution money. The procedure for paying monthly salaries to working employees in a public private partnership-based non-governmental preschool organization is paid like the monthly salaries of workers in public preschool organizations, but DXS can also be paid monthly, based on an agreement between the working employee and the director of the DXSH, as opposed to DMTTS. In this case, depending on the correct Organization of work based on the specialty of the worker of the preschool educational organization, increasing the number of pupils in the group with the involvement of children and achieving the result in the educational process, monthly salaries are carried out by the director of the DPRK, and other incentives are also carried out by the director. Such a transaction is carried out not only with caregivers, but also depending on the work activities of other working employees. This regulation is not followed in public preschool organizations, where all working employees are paid the same monthly salary as prescribed, and are encouraged in an amount of 10 percent each month.

The state allocates a subsidy of up to 50 percent for the costs spent on each child being brought up in the DPRK. DXSH NMTT is exempt from land-property taxes for up to 10 years, and compensation is paid monthly from the state party at a rate of 50 percent for each child attending MTT.

Procedure for choosing a private partner in the organization of a public-private partnership.³

The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Resolution No. 259 “on improving the procedure for the implementation of public-private partnership projects” on April 26, 2020. This charter consists of a total of 15 chapter 82 points.

This regulation establishes the procedure for the development, consideration, initiative, selection of a private partner, registration of public private partnership projects and their implementation of all existing public-private partnership projects. The cost of a project proposed by a legal entity or private person includes the size of construction, service and investments made. The land and rental areas granted by the state are not part of the project's value.

The project is initially evaluated by a state partner, the MT Ministry. This will consider the opportunities that DXSh can implement on a project basis. The project must be able to meet the

² <https://elib.buxdu.uz/index.php/pages/referatlar-mustaqil-ish-kurs-ishi/item/12317-tavakkalchilikni-boshqarish>

³ Quchqorova N.M. Tarbiyachi-pedagoglarda iqtisodiy-huquqiy kompetentlikni rivojlantirish. Darslik. “BOOKMANY PRINT” Toshkent-2022. 139-140-betlar

following conditions:

should be aimed at solving economic, social and infrastructure-related tasks;

work on these projects will be carried out by ministries, government agencies, local executive authorities;

work on the project under consideration, the quality of services and high relative to current indicators:

compliance with the contract deadline;

The property rights to the DXSh building shall be within the jurisdiction of the MT Ministry;

the level of financial support of the project;

acceptance of non-governmental investments:

requirements and needs for the project, the review of;

consideration of the problems arising in the implementation of the project;

availability of high management experience;

A public-private partnership project can be proposed by a public partner and a private partner. If necessary, a legal entity can propose a project, in agreement with other business entities as a team. The rights and obligations of team members are given in the contract for the organization of the team.

Establishment of a family preschool organization

Today, in order to purposefully, systematically establish the educational system in our society, especially organizations that carry out their activities in the preschool education system and the activities dedicated to education and education in them, further develop any forms of MTTs, as well as to increase the level of coverage of children brought up at this stage of education on a large scale and thus carefully prepare "In order to strengthen the material and technical base of the preschool education system, improve the quality of the provision of preschool services to the population and increase the share of the non-governmental sector in the field: "in order to expand the network of preschool educational organizations in districts with low coverage levels on additional measures"⁴ PQ-5144 of June 10, 2021 was adopted by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The inclusion of children in the preschool system in our country is not an exaggeration, especially if we say that the family is developing on the basis of non-governmental preschool organizations.

Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 2, 2022 No. 426 "on measures to simplify public-private partnership relations in the field of preschool education using modern digital technologies" was adopted.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. Currently, in our country, along with the DMTT, the demand for non-governmental preschool organizations is also very increasing. The main goal of organizing family non-governmental MTTs is to increase the level of coverage, to grow a harmonious generation in every possible way. By establishing family preschool organizations, an entrepreneur who has opened a family MTT will be able to provide some benefit to his family budget, as well as provide employment for unemployed women. The family disposes of the property that is hidden in the preschool educational institution and the property acquired in the funds allocated to it according to the legislation.

It must be said that our President Sh. In his speech, Mirziyoyev said, "every job is important to

⁴ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2021-yil 10-iyundagi PQ-5144 – son qarori

us. Loqal we are ready to raise in our head the entrepreneur who employed two people. Because the employment of a person is the basis for the fact that his family will be prosperous, and the next day, his confidence in the state will increase”.

Now in our country there are several facilities for young entrepreneurs, especially our future educators, to start their own business. Each entrepreneur can employ unemployed women by opening a family MTT, helping to cover children with MTT. As a result of the conditions provided by our state, due to the innovations and benefits carried out in the MT system, now not only DMTT, zero in private, public-private partnership opened family MTTS are also achieving very good results in development. Day by day, the demand for non-governmental preschool organizations is also increasing. Taking advantage of these opportunities, each entrepreneurial educator will be able to start his own affordable businesses.

The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated August 2, 2022 “on measures to simplify public-private partnership relations in the field of preschool education using modern digital technologies” No. 426 makes it clear in the decision that it will be automatically calculated in the information system for the management of non-state MTTS. In this case, the calculation of the attendance of pedagogical personnel at work and the carrying out of the attendance of children is carried out using the technology of biometric identification of the individual through a mobile application.

In this decision, a regulation on Family Non-Governmental MTT lari was developed. The charter specifies the purpose, tasks, Organization of their activities, provision of material and technical base and methodological side, financing, as well as the procedure for their management. The organization of family MTT activities is carried out in accordance with the following requirements.

ANALYZES AND RESULTS.

PROCEDURE FOR USING NMTTBAT (ELECTRONIC APPLICATION)

In the current period, the head of the family MTT will electronically download NMTTBAT's mobile app to use Nmttbat and, having entered Nmttbat using Nmttbat's internet site or mobile app, familiarize himself with the requirements and conditions outlined in it, express his consent based on the use of data and confirm it through his electronic digital signature. In this case, a personal cabinet will be opened in the name of the director of the MTT in Nmttbat.⁵ So today, our future educators in the desire to become entrepreneurs are family MTT to open up, it is necessary that they are well versed in these legislation and have also mastered the use of digital technologies.

FAMILY MTT OPENING PROCEDURE.

1. The applicant wishing to open a family MTT sends an electronic application to the information system that manages non-state MTT's.
2. Information system that manages non-public MTTS.
 1. The entrepreneur is sent an email marked in the application or, if not, information on his mobile phone, the ID of the application and the date and time of receipt of the application.
 2. Requests are made electronically to the SEOM and Fire Safety Authority.
 3. SEOM and the fire safety authority place the conclusions about whether or not the planned location to open the family MTT in an electronic NMTT managing information system.
 4. After receiving the conclusions of the NMTTBATSEO and the Fire Safety Authority, the application is sent to MTV via NMTTBAT.

⁵ Vazirlar Mahkamasining “Maktabgacha ta’lim sohasida davlat-xususiy sheriklik munosabatlarini zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida soddalashtirish chora-tadbirlari to’g’risida”gi 2022-yil 2-avgustdagi 426-son qarori

5. Having studied the information about the number of preschool children at the address where the opening of MTVOMTT is determined, about the number of children covered or not covered by the state and NMTTS located in the same place, the family puts in NMTTBAT the conclusion that the opening of OMTT to the MTT is expedient or not.

6. The positive conclusion of MTV is that an agreement on public-private partnership is automatically formed to NMTTBAT and sends a message electronically to a private partner for signing.

7. This transaction is automatically sent to the state partner for electronic signature after NMTTBAT has electronically signed the transaction placed in the private partner Nmttbat.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it should be said that preschool education specialists with higher education, on the other hand, are limited to being educators in public MTTs or in private MTTs organized by entrepreneurs from another field. Based on social needs, it serves to clarify the principles of methodological, organizational, management in the process of developing economic competence, effectively solve the development of indicators of economic competence of future educators. Each future educator is obliged to know the concepts for the development of economic and legal consciousness in MTTs: estimates, salaries, outsourcing, as well as the types of educational organizations of the state preschool educational institution and the methodology for their organization. The use of digital technologies in this process makes it possible to prevent corruption cases, make good use of time and eliminate pedagogical risks.

The organization of family preschool organizations is important in expanding and expanding the reach of children. Because it is impossible to cover all children to public preschool organizations too. Every future educator who says that I will be the most enterprising progressive educator of the day will be able to create his own business in the future if he carefully obtains all the information presented above and fulfill his goals in order without any difficulties. Each family preschool educational organization is attached to the base DMTTs to improve the knowledge, skills and skills of its educators. With this, many effective results can be achieved.

Bibliography

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasining "Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya to'g'risida" gi O'RQ-595-son 2019 yil 16-dekabr
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2021-yil 10-iyundagi PQ-5144 – son qarori
3. Vazirlar Mahkamasining "Maktabgacha ta'lim sohasida davlat-xususiy sheriklik munosabatlarini zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida soddalashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi 2022-yil 2-avgustdagi 426-son qarori
4. Vazirlar Mahkamasining "Maktabgacha ta'lim sohasida davlat-xususiy sheriklik munosabatlarini zamonaviy raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida soddalashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi 2022-yil 2-avgustdagi 426-son qarori
5. Kadirova M.R. Tibbiy ta'lim jarayonida kasbiy kompetentlikni metodik takomillashtirish texnologiyalar (tibbiyotda pedagogikani o'qitish misolida) Ped.fanl.d-ri (DSc) dis. avtoref. – Namangan – 2022. 38-bet
6. Quchqorova N.M. Tarbiyachi-pedagoglarda iqtisodiy-huquqiy kompetentlikni rivojlantirish. Darslik. "BOOKMANY PRINT" Toshkent-2022. 139-140-betlar
7. Quchqorova N.M. Development of the economic culture of future primary school teachers on the basis of an integrated approach. Ped. fanl. fal. Doc.(PhD) diss. autoref. - Nukus-2020. P. 58-59-83

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8. Quchqorova N.M. Components and criteria of economic culture of future teachers. E3S Web of Conferences 402, 08003 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202340208003>. *TransSiberia 2023*
 9. www.ziyonet.uz
 10. www.pedagog.uz